

Intolerance of Uncertainty and Mental Well-being: Important Role of Loneliness and Fear of COVID-19: Evidence from Higher Educational Institutions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 11, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Loneliness, Mental Wellbeing, Fear of COVID-19, Intolerance to Uncertainty</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4750645</p>	<p><i>The novel COVID-19 impacted the mental, social, psychological, and emotional wellbeing of every individual living in this earth. In the present scenario, irrespective of the other factors, COVID-19 is the primary root cause of certain dominant factors like uncertainty, fear, isolation, loneliness, stress, anxiety, depression, and trauma that adversely affect our lives. This study, therefore, explored whether uncertainty affects an individual's mental wellbeing. Through a sequential mediation mechanism, we examined whether loneliness and fear of COVID-19 serially mediate the relationship between uncertainty and wellbeing. A time-lag research design using mediation analyses was conducted. A data from 683 participants working in diverse universities and colleges were collected in three waves. We found that intolerance to uncertainty is negatively related to mental wellbeing. This relationship is sequentially mediated by loneliness and fear of COVID-19, such that loneliness increases the fear of COVID-19, ultimately leading to adversely affecting mental wellbeing. Based on the findings, it is concluded that intolerance to uncertainty, loneliness, and fear of COVID-19 harm mental wellbeing. Further, loneliness heaves COVID-19 fear that may lead to disrupts wellbeing.</i></p>

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has entirely affected the routine life of every individual. Many governments impose certain restrictions on the general public like masks facing, social distancing, smart lockdown, and quarantining to reduce the spread of COVID-19 (Pakpour and Griffiths, 2020; Asmundson and Taylor, 2020). The routine activities such as performing their jobs, running their businesses, social gathering, and even dating and loving your co-partner of ordinary people are severely affected. This virus affects not only the social lives but also the psychological and mental health of peoples in the form of stress, coping, and trauma (Khattak et al., 2020; Garfin et al., 2020). Past studies show that many people experienced psychological disorders after the SARS outbreak (Mihashi et al., 2009). During the SARS outbreak, two primary psychological dysfunctions, i.e., delayed dysfunction and chronic dysfunction, were reported among patients (Bonanno, 2012). Main et al. (2011) argued that the SARS-related stressor checklist and psychological symptoms checklist has a positive association.

During pandemics, the potential risk that individuals consider as the chances of infection leads to adverse psychological consequences. The COVID-19, a life-threatening virus, spread quickly among peoples that severely affects their mental and psychological well-being. A similar finding was reported in the near past (Ngade et al., 2017) when the Ebola epidemic hits Africa intensively. The local people were prone to experience stress, anxiety, trauma, and Ebola-related worry. Incremental suicide cases were observed during the Ebola epidemic, with the fear that their beloved ones will be infected (Yip et al., 2010). The same phenomenon is repeated in the COVID-19 case as people have a higher fear of COVID-19 committed and attempted suicide intending to be infected (Mamun and Griffiths, 2020).

Like other epidemics, the novel COVID-19 pandemic also negatively affects the mental and psychological wellbeing's of individuals in the shape of anxiety, stress, secondary trauma, intolerance of uncertainty, and depression (Mckay et al., 2020; Satıcı et al., 2020). The psychological effects of COVID-19 pandemic are more profound in countries where people are more health-conscious or where the fear of COVID-19 is high (Zhao et al., 2020; Ji and An, 2020). Moreover, the sternness of fear was influenced by gender, age, mental resilience, and the body's immune system.

Like the rest of the world, people in Pakistan are prone to higher risk and fear of COVID-19 infection. The people found themselves caught between a rock and a hard place as they have the limited market opportunity and medical supply. Certain dominant factors that emerged from COVID-19 affect individuals' social lives, including smart lockdown, excessive hand washings, quarantine, loneliness, social distancing, face

mask, hands shaking, hugging, panic purchasing and social withdrawal (Asmundson and Tayloy, 2020). The fear among the country's people is reached at the peak level due to a massive media campaign by the government against COVID-19. Grounded on the theory of response styles (Nolen-Hoeksema et al., 2008), the present research as an attempt to provide a blueprint of how intolerance to uncertainty affects individual wellbeing. Moreover, this attempt is the calls for a paper by Satici et al. (2020). We explored the intervening mechanism on the relationship between intolerance to uncertainty and an individual's wellbeing using time-lag research design. We expect that loneliness and fear of COVID-19 act as possible intervening variables that affect the relationship between uncertainty and wellbeing.

2. Hypotheses Development

From the past few decades, researchers defined and operationalized well-being and its dimensions (Tennant et al., 2007). Research related to well-being is based on two main pillars, i.e., hedonic and eudaimonic (e.g., Waterman et al., 2010; Bastian et al., 2014). However, in recent years, these two concepts were used interchangeably (Lambert et al., 2015; Disabato et al., 2016). The idea of mental wellbeing is based on psychological constructs that emerge from these two main approaches (Tennant et al., 2007). Psychological functioning, emotional and cognitive dimensions of well-being constitute mental wellbeing. In our case, we expected that in the current pandemic, intolerance to uncertainty is the significant determinant of psychological well-being.

Intolerance to uncertainty (ITU) is characterized as dispositional fear, which underlies emotions and contributes to anxiety when the unknown is strongly perceived (Hong and Lee, 2015). In an ambiguous situation like the current one, ITU captures an adverse reaction irrespective of the logical probability of the real phenomenon. In this regard, intolerance to uncertainty is considered the primary driver of anxiety among individuals (Hollingsworth et al., 2018). Besides this, it also positively effects secondary traumatic stress disorder on depression (Morriss et al., 2016). Based on the above literature, we expect that ITU has a negative association with wellbeing. Though introducing the intervening mechanism in this relationship is of great utility.

Researchers argued that loneliness is the sum of two main characteristics. First, loneliness is the negative affective states (e.g., sadness or anxiety) arouses from aversive experience. Second, loneliness is an individual's perception of measurable deficiencies in social networks (Menec et al., 2019; De Jong et al., 2015). These deficiencies can be due to social loneliness – feeling isolation in the social network and or emotional loneliness – loss of close relationship (Brimelow and Wollin, 2017). Loneliness individual has faced specific issues like loss of social contacts, health problems, depression, stress, loss focus on work, and genetic predispositions. A plethora of research highlights that loneliness has adverse effects on physical and mental health including stress perception (Huang et al., 2019; Gan et al., 2015), cardiovascular diseases (Christiansen et al., 2016; Wolf and Davis, 2014), depression (Hegeman et al., 2018; Niu et al., 2018), and suicide ideation (Valtorta et al., 2018; Stickley and Koyanagi, 2016). Further, it is also associated with obesity or smoking, and less physical activity leads to developing chronic diseases and, afterward, leads to more psychological distress (Niedzwiedz et al., 2016; Richard et al., 2017).

In the same way, past researches also highlighted that loneliness is the considerable risk factor of depression in senior citizens (Zhao et al., 2020; Stamatis et al., 2020; Brimelow and Wollin, 2017). Jongenelis et al., (2004), concluded that lack of perceived support and loneliness are the main factors that accompany depression. Martinsson, (2012), argued that harmonious and stable relationship is the protective factor to prevent depression and loneliness among individuals. A multiple-wave study of Tsai et al. (2014) concluded that rapid urbanization and industrialization and increased loneliness lead to increased depression, which affects mental wellbeing. Therefore, in this research, we hypothesized that loneliness nourished by uncertainty might adversely affect wellbeing through fear of COVID-19. As mentioned earlier, the ministry of health exerts a massive campaign over media against COVID-19 may also increase the worry and stress among the general public. This quick transmission of information related to COVID-19 in both traditional and social media leads to increased uncertainty. Accordingly, the inherent negativities of the current COVID-19 pandemic deteriorate the psychological wellbeing of a common man. Thus, based on the cited literature, we proposed the following hypotheses:

H1: Intolerance to uncertainty is significantly but negatively related to mental wellbeing

H2: Loneliness mediates the relationship of intolerance to uncertainty and mental wellbeing

H3: Fear of COVID-19 mediates the association of intolerance to uncertainty and mental wellbeing

H4: Loneliness and Fear of COVID-19 sequentially mediates the relationship of intolerance to uncertainty and mental wellbeing

H2

H3

H1

Intolerance to Uncertainty Figure 1: Proposed Conceptual Framework Mental-Wellbeing

3. Methods

3.1. Sample and Procedure

Data were collected from higher educational institutions, including universities and colleges operated in two major cities of Pakistan, i.e., Islamabad and Rawalpindi. There were two reasons to select these organizations. First, the respondent’s minimum bachelor qualifications. As we use an English base survey instrument for data collection, thus, respondents having higher qualifications have no issue to fill the survey instrument. Second, our purpose was to assess the perception of the general public; thus, we select both universities and colleges from twin cities, i.e., Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Initially, we plan to collect the response of 2000 peoples. Respondents were assured about their response’s confidentiality and tell them the purpose and expected outcomes of the study. Based on a quasi-experimental design (time-lag), we collect the data in three waves to avoid the respondent’s biases. In the first interval (T1), we distributed 2000 questionnaires among the target sample to assess their uncertainty level. After 3 weeks break from T1, we contacted the same respondents in the second interval (T2), to know about their loneliness and fear of COVID-19 level. Similarly, in the third interval (T3), which occurred three weeks after the second interval, we approached the same respondents to fill the survey instrument related to their mental well-being. In the first round, we received 1268 valid responses with a response rate of 63.4%. In the second round, we received 824 responses with a response rate of 41.2%. In the final round, we received 683 responses with a response rate of 34.15%. The total data collection period was three months, i.e., from March to May 2020. Demographic statistics are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Demographic Statistics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	520	76%
Female	163	23.8%
Education		
Bachelor	128	18.7%
Master	200	29.3%
M.Phil.	293	42.8%
PhD	62	9.07%
Occupation		
Government Employee	326	47.7%
Private Employee	357	52.3%
Material Status		
Single	472	69%
Married	211	31%
COVID Symptoms		
Yes	43	6.3%
No	512	75%
Partially	128	18.7%

3.2. Measures

3.2.1. Intolerance to Uncertainty

To assess participants' intolerance to uncertainty level, we adapt a Short Version scale developed by Carleton et al., (2007). This scale has 12 items and was measured on a five-point Likert scale comprising 1 "not at all characteristic of me" to 5 "entirely characteristic of me." The sample item is "When I am uncertain, I can't function very well." Past researches also used this scale and found excellent reliability, e.g., ($\alpha = .87$) (Satici et al., 2020).

3.2.2. Mental Well-being

A 14 items scale developed by Tennant et al. (2007) was adapted to measure the mental well-being of the study participants. Participants were score on 1 "none of the time" to 5 "all of the time." The sample item is "I've been feeling relax." Past studies used this scale to assess mental wellbeing and found good reliability score, e.g., ($\alpha = .92$), (Keldal, 2015).

3.3.3. Loneliness

To assess participants' loneliness, we adapt the 11 items of loneliness scale developed by Gierveld and Tilburg (1999). Respondents' responses were score on 1 "yes" to 5 "no." The sample item is "I miss having a really close friend." Previous studies found an excellent reliability score of this scale, e.g., ($\alpha = .94$) (Frinking et al., 2019).

3.3.4. Fear of COVID-19

To assess fear of COVID-19, we adapt a seven items scale developed by Ahoru et al., (2020). The sample item is "How much does your illness affect you emotionally." A good reliability score was observed for this scale by previous researchers, e.g., ($\alpha = .87$), (Satici et al., 2020).

4. Results

Table 2 shows the confirmatory factor analysis of each study variable. The results revealed that independent variable intolerance to uncertainty has a good model fit as all the model fit values are according to a minimum and maximum threshold. Dependent variable mental-wellbeing and both mediating variables i.e., existential loneliness and COVID-19 fear, also have good model fit. Moreover, results show that data have a good model fit.

Table 2: Individual Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Name of Variable	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	CFI	TLI	NFI	GFI	AGFI	RMR	RMSEA	AVE
COVID-19 Fear	13.31	12	1.11	.976	.942	.921	.925	.906	.051	.075	0.65
Intolerance to Uncertainty	99.26	47	2.11	.943	.941	.915	.909	.889	.056	.080	0.69
Loneliness	21.21	13	1.63	.958	.921	.930	.910	.904	.057	.079	0.70
Mental-Wellbeing	91.20	45	2.03	.978	.929	.939	.919	.904	.062	.059	0.79

Table 3 shows the paired confirmatory factor analysis of the variables of the study. It comprises Harman's factor test results. Different research studies indicate that Harman's test is an excellent method to find common method variance (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, and Podsakoff, 2003). In Harman's test, all items of the variables are loaded on one factor and then compared it with the two factors, three-factor, and four factors. This study has four variables; therefore, in this study, we tested up to the four-factor model. Harman's test contained independent variable intolerance to uncertainty, dependent variable mental-wellbeing, and mediating variables existential loneliness and COVID-19 fear. Harman's test results revealed that 2 factors, 3 factors, and 4-factor model have good model fit compared to their 1 factor. The bold values in the table show a good model fit.

Table 3: Paired Comparison CFA

Name of Variable	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	CFI	TLI	NFI	GFI	AGFI	RMR	RMSEA
2 factor (IU+EL)	175.87	79	2.226	.929	.900	.912	.901	.889	.049	.074
1 factor (IU+EL)	721.63	61	11.830	.499	.399	.440	.401	.398	.426	.201
3 Factor (IU+EL+CVOID-19)	401.32	259	1.549	.959	.931	.909	.902	.900	.060	.077
1 Factor (IU+EL+CVOID-19)	1576.84	199	7.923	.403	.400	.412	.489	.437	.326	.254
4 Factor (IU+EL+CVOID-19+MW)	801.74	672	1.193	.953	.928	.929	.920	.900	.053	.073
1 Factor (IU+EL+CVOID-19+MW)	2749.68	359	7.659	.532	.501	.521	.499	.478	.148	.138

Table 4 highlighted below represents the descriptive statistics, reliabilities, and bivariate correlations among the study variables. As seen, mental well-being is negatively associated with intolerance to uncertainty ($\gamma = -.32, p < .05$), fear of COVID-19 ($\gamma = -.27, p < .05$), and loneliness ($\gamma = -.22, p < .05$). Intolerance to uncertainty is positively associated with fear of COVID-19 ($\gamma = .45, p < .05$), and loneliness ($\gamma = .38, p < .05$). Alpha values are reported in the right diagonal in parentheses. All values are above the suggested value indicating an excellent reliability score. The values of skewness (SK) and kurtosis (KR) also fall in the suggested range; thus, ensure data normality.

Table 4: Descriptive, Correlation and Alpha

Mean	SD	SK	KR	1	2	3	4
1. Mental Wellbeing				3.38	.984	-.410	.630 (.84)

2. Intolerance to Uncertainty	3.20	1.10	-.280	-.132	-.32**	(.86)
3. Fear of COVID-19	3.28	1.04	.312	-.310	-.27	.45** (.89)
4. Loneliness	3.18	1.08	.511	.320	-.22	.38** .52** (.91)

Note: SK (skewness), KR (kurtosis), reliability is reported in parentheses, * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$, ($n = 683$)

4.1. Test of Hypotheses

To test the study hypotheses, we follow Preacher and Hayes (2013) method. For a model like the current study has, they suggested applying model 6 from PROCESS macro. Table 5 reports the results of direct and sequential mediation analysis. As depicted, intolerance to uncertainty is negatively related to mental well-being ($\beta = -.342$, $p < .05$), with a 95% confidence interval; thus, we received support for H1. When loneliness and fear of COVID-19 were interred in the model as mediators, the coefficient was still significant, i.e., (direct effect, $\beta = -.092$, $p < .05$). We found a positive and significant relationship between ITU and loneliness ($\beta = .217$, $p < .05$), and between ITU and fear of COVID-19 ($\beta = .193$, $p < .05$).

We found a significant indirect effect of ITU on MW through loneliness ($\beta = -.110$, $p < .05$); thus, H2 was supported. Furthermore, the indirect impact of ITU on MW via fear of COVID-19 is also significant ($\beta = -.092$, $p < .05$), leading to support H3. Finally, sequential mediation hypotheses were tested. We found that the indirect effect of ITU on MW via loneliness and fear of COVID-19 is significant ($\beta = -.231$, $p < .05$); thus, we received support for H4.

Table 5: Sequential Mediation

Relationship	Coeff.	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
ITU → MW	-.342	.09	-3.8	.00	-.294	-.131
ITU → Lon → MW	-.110	.04	-2.6	.00	-.118	-.054
ITU → FC → MW	-.092	.02	-4.6	.00	-.082	-.032
ITU → Lon → FC → MW	-.231	.11	-2.1	.01	-.040	-.026

ITU = Intolerance to Uncertainty, MW = Mental Wellbeing, Lon = Loneliness, Fc = Fear of COVID-19

5. Discussion

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 is the global pandemic as it spread quickly throughout the world. Consequently, it negatively impacted every individual's mental, psychological, and emotional health. Therefore, the current research investigated the impact of ITU, loneliness, fear of COVID-19, and the mental well-being of the general public in Pakistani context. Pakistan is at number 12th in the world having a higher number of confirmed cases, and at number 2nd position in South Asia, and placed in the 3rd position in Asia. At present, the number of confirmed cases reported on Official web has reached to 2,93711 till August 25, 2020 (www.covid.gov.pk). Despite the higher ratio of confirmed cases, the death ratio is comparatively low, i.e., 2.14% compared to a global average of 3.9%. The higher numbers of confirmed cases created a big worry in the local community and restricted them to homes. This social isolation makes them depressed and creates anxiety and stress leading to adverse psychological and mental disorders.

Our findings suggest that ITU is negatively related to mental well-being. Further, we found that loneliness and fear of COVID-19 plays an intervening role in the link between ITU and mental well-being. The results fully supported our proposed model (see Figure 1). Our findings related to negative psychological consequences during pandemics are consistent with past studies (e.g., Satici et al., 2020). Individual risk perception and direct and indirect trauma threatened mental and psychological well-being. In an unclear situation like the present one, ITU captures an adverse reaction irrespective of the logical probability of the real phenomenon. In this regard, ITU is considered the primary driver of anxiety among individuals (Hollingsworth et al., 2018). Besides this, it also positively effects secondary traumatic stress disorder on depression. Our central hypothesis that was the sequential mediation roles of loneliness and fear of COVID-19 on the link between ITU and wellbeing was confirmed. In the same line, we found that loneliness swells COVID-19 fear that may lead to disrupts wellbeing.

5.1. Limitations and Future Directions

Apart from this, we contribute to the existing body of knowledge, and some potential flaws must be addressed in future studies. First, we did not control for age and gender as past studies show that loneliness and fear are at a high level among senior citizens and women (e.g., Frinking et al., 2019; Gan et al., 2015). It is suggested to replicate the existing framework by controlling for certain variables like age and gender and then comparing the differences among them. Second, we used loneliness as a composite variable and failed to check the individual effect of each dimension of loneliness on well-being, i.e., social loneliness and emotional loneliness. Researchers are invited to expend our model by selecting both types of loneliness to polish the existing model further. Third, we check sequential mediation roles of loneliness and fear of COVID-19 and found that loneliness may increase the fear that finally affects mental well-being. Other potential mediators like meaningfulness and psychological need frustration may be used in future studies. Lastly, we explore this phenomenon in Pakistan. One may replicate our model in other cultures and settings to further generalize our findings.

5.2. Conclusion

The present research sheds light on how uncertainty impacts the mental well-being of people. The present research attempted to provide a design of how ITU affects individual well-being. Besides this, we explored the intervening variables on the relationship between ITU and an individual's wellbeing. We found that loneliness and fear of COVID-19 act as possible intervening variables that affect the relationship between ITU and well-being. Finally, we concluded that loneliness might increase the fear of the COVID-19 pandemic. We offer suggestions to the government and other governing institutions to enhance the general public's motivation level through counseling programs related to individual positive psychological state. By doing so, the government can share the latest research about COVID-19. Further, instead, to create uncertainty about COVID-19, the government should encourage the local community to fight against COVID-19.

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